

IMPLEMENTATION OF LEAN METHODOLOGY IN SALES

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Abstract

Purpose – *The aim of this work is to investigate the possibility to implement the lean methodology in sales.*

Methodology/approach – *The main concepts of lean manufacturing were examined: types of waste, lean principles, 5 s. The sales process/cycle were described from the point of view of creating added value instead of waste. The lean concepts were transposed at the level of sales process and sales cycle. The manner how theoretical aspects are implemented in the sales were investigated for six companies which sell doors. The companies are located in Cluj Napoca and Alba Iulia and some of them have more selling points. The investigation took place in june – august 2020.*

Findings – *All eight types of waste can be found in sales. They generate supplementary costs, time delay and the possibility of not closing the deal. It was revealed a gap between what means added value for customer and what perceives the sales force.*

Research limitations/implications – *The main limitation was generated by the actual situation regarding social distancing. It was not possible to cover a higher number of sellers or to discuss with managers at top level. The persons involved in the study were executives in sales. The study must be extended for the sales of other products and services.*

Practical implications – *The work provides to the sales businesses a direction to increase their competitiveness by implementing lean methodology in sales.*

Originality/value – *The results provide managerial information for organizing better sales processes and for developing lean sales cycles.*

Key words: *lean methodology, performance, sales*

Introduction

Increasing the sales performance is one of the main goals of a competitive organization. The central idea of the majority implemented methods is to evaluate and increase the performance at the salesforce level. A better approach is to consider the entire organization as a system and to apply the lean principles. A continuous improvement of sales is obtained by finding and decrease or eliminate the causes that affect the results.

Trends in the management of sales

The development of the markets and the increased competition determined new trends in management of sales. Some of the changes at the process level are related with the shift from transaction to relationship, from individual person to the team level, from volume of sales to the productivity of sales, from management to leadership and from local approach to a global approach. (Baker, 2008)

At the managerial level, in the past, the managers were focused to command and control the activities. Nowadays, the importance of the knowledge at company level become more important than the physical resources. The delegation of responsibility is very often used as leading method. The change was necessary because the clients have less patience in the sales process, it is much easier to sell for all

companies and the success is determined by partnership and long-term relations. The manager is more and more a facilitator in the sales process.

The role of the sales team was transferred to the sales centers. The sales team has a permanent character, the salesforce is stable in the team and has a strategic mission from organizational point of view. The sales center is temporary. Its advantage is to exploit better the sales opportunities, to have a variable membership of the sales force and to be transaction oriented. The center mission is a tactical one.

Lean elements

Lean manufacturing is not a general receipt for goal accomplishment. Many organizations implement lean principles, but this is not a guarantee of achieving all purposed targets from the point of view of content and time constrain. The elimination of non-value added elements from processes is the central idea of lean. The company will have competitive advantage by eliminating the waste at all levels and stages. The sales process can be continuously improved in this manner.

Lean types of waste

Taiichi Ohno (1988) and Shigeo Shingo (1981) established the Toyota famous production systems. Ohno proposed the framework of lean manufacturing. The central idea was to obtain higher results with less resources and effort. The value was defined through the eyes of customers. The concept of waste means everything which does not bring value for the customer. Seven types of waste were defined at the beginning, latter on an eighth one was added. The eighth type of waste is related with the capacity of management to correctly use the human potential of personnel. The first seven types are related with production process.

DOWNTIME is the acronym for the lean types of waste. Their meaning is the following: defects, overproduction, waiting, not utilizing the human talent, transportation, inventory in excess, motion waste and excess processing. Defects are generated by lack or low standards, bad processes, weak documentation or low-quality control. Overproduction has as reasons a wrong understanding of customer needs, a bad forecasting of demand, unreliable processes, long set-up time. Waiting is related with persons and materials. Not utilizing the human talent appears because of poor management, lack of training, assignment of wrong task to the wrong employee and improper communication process.

The transportation is connected more with the manufacturing plant and is determined by a wrong layout and the existence of multiple storage facilities. It can produce damages of the transported goods and a cost increase. The excess of inventory appears because of overproduction, a wrong connection between purchasing and production, wrong done inventories. The wrong motion of raw materials, equipment and persons have as results non added value time and additional unwanted costs. The supply chain has a moderate capacity to absorb the risks in a traditional organization. (Parthipan, 2015) Last but not least, the excess processing can appear because of insufficient standards, human errors, communications and over reporting.

Lean principles

There are five lean principles. They were proposed by Womak and Jones. These principles are: define and identify the value, map the value stream, create the flow after eliminating the waste from the value stream, establish pull, seek perfection and make lean a part of the organizational culture. The value must be expressed in terms of a specific product or service. The flow has to be continuous for products, services and information.

Lean Sales

The most important aspect which one need to determine is if the sales process creates added value or waste. This is necessary because value and waste are key concepts in lean. The elements which can generate waste mentioned for the sales process are the following (Nissila, 2013):

1. Degree of customization: different customers have different needs and desires. The correctness of market segmentation is very important for an efficient sales process. Some clients can ask for customized products and services. These maybe do not produce so much disturbance for the salesforce, but the effects are much greater at manufacturing and delivery level. The

salesman must try to discover why the client asks for a specific customization and try to avoid it if it is not mandatory for the client.

2. Work partially done: there are too many tasks in progress and nothing to be delivered. The sales process requires many contacts with the customers, many reports, meetings and emails. All of them involve time and energy and generate costs. The unfinished tasks will influence and create other unfinished jobs.
3. Re-Learn: in a sales team there are persons who already know how to accomplish some tasks, but these tasks are assigned to other persons less qualified in that topic. The time necessary to learn and the mistakes that can appear lower the added value of the sales process.
4. Task switching: the team leader must ask a person to do just one thing at one time and not to switch that person from a task to another one. Confusion and mistakes can be generated. Work partially done and re-learning are associated with task switching.
5. Delays: the customers can postpone some tasks because of other priorities they have in their company. This will affect the sales team and the sales process without being possible to avoid it.
6. Defects: the defects which occurs in the sales process are dangerous because very often the client will choose another provider and the company will not have the opportunity to correct the problem.

The five lean principles have correspondence for the sales process. To identify the value for the customer means to do market segmentation and identify the target market. To map the value stream means to attempt a value stream mapping having in mind the potential opportunities. To create the flow is to have a non-disruptive flow for the offer. Establish pull is obtained by delivering only what the client required. To acquire the customer is equal with seek perfection.

Sales Cycle

All activities which are related with closing a sale are included in the sales cycle. There are many definitions of sales cycle. It can be defined as the time from the moment of first approach until the moment of selling. Other definition says the sales cycle is a sequence of predictable stages in order to sell a product. The length of the sales process is very important. A more effective sales department will obtain shorter length of sales cycle than the average of competitors. A longer time to close a sale is very bad because the customer can change his mind or can close the deal with a competitor.

There are seven phases of a sales cycle: prospecting for customers, contact the potential customers, qualify the customer in order to see if he has decision power, presentation of the products and services provided by the company, facing the clients' objections, closing the sale and obtain referrals. The management of sales cycles has as goal the decrease of its time. The literature review mentions the length of a conventional sales cycle as four to six months. A short cycle means less than a month and a long one covers more than twelve months. (Each phase of the cycle must be analyzed. The conversion rate helps us to calculate which stage is the longest. The conversion rate is defined as the ratio between the number of opportunities in one stage and the number in the following stage. It is measured in percentages. (Bean, 2019)

Lean Approach of Sales Cycle

An analysis from the lean point of view, regarding the sales cycle, revealed that the representatives spend only 37% of their time selling. The rest of the time is covered by the administrative and other tasks which generate more types of lean waste in the sales process. Eighty percent of the salesman declared that they need about five meetings in order to close a deal but 44% of them give up after the first appointment. These figures indicate a requirement for increasing the number of representatives who can follow all steps of sales cycle.

A lean approach of sales cycle group the above mentioned seven phases in three stages: the pre-sales activity, the direct selling activity and the post-sales engagement. The sales force and the marketing department work together in the pre-sales activity. Their goals are to increase the customization level and to deliver a standard approach for as many as possible activities. On the other hand, the tasks for each person are correlated with the knowledge and experience of each salesmen, decreasing in this way the non-utilizing the human talent. The main result will be the decrease of time for each step. Decreasing time and waste means implementation of lean in pre-sales activity. To map the selling

process and to create the flow are the main concerns in the direct selling activity. Each salesman who had good result could design standard work and to implement best practices in their activity. Another important aspect for this stage is to monitor the performance of each person and/or team according with the standard key performance indices. The post sales engagement is mandatory after closing the deal. It is not enough to provide automatic order confirmation to the customer. The marketing team must keep on the contact with the client for loyalty programs and referrals. The communication process will consider the lean aspect by eliminating the time and multiple contacts with the same person for the same reasons. (Eisenhart, 2016)

Discussion and conclusions

A study was done in order to investigate if and at which level, the elements of lean methodology are used in sales process of doors. Five companies located in Cluj Napoca and one from Alba Iulia were analyzed. Some of the selected companies have more selling point. It was expected to have the same approach in all selling points, but the results were very different. The selling doors process was selected because the construction sector registers a significant growth. The names of the companies and of the salesmen are not revealed due to confidentiality reasons. They will be called Company A – the one from Alba Iulia, Company B, C, D, E and F – the ones from Cluj Napoca. The letters were assigned according with the alphabetical real name. Company B is a small one, companies C, D and E are big companies and F is a medium size company. E and F firms have more selling points. The discussions took place with salesmen after observing their behavior with the clients and the customer approach manner.

All the salesmen mentioned the existence of in-process waste because they are doing tasks which donot bring added value to their goal. A low efficiency and the existence of mistakes was recognized in four companies. Very often, many of the same sales process stages are not done in the same way each time. A medium to high degree of inconsistency was discovered. Only the company A offers a high degree of customization for the customers, fact providing great added value. The company offers different sizes, different colors or glass type and design. The customer is not obliged to reconstruct the wall area for the door. The re-learn waste was not observed for the big companies but it was revealed in the small and medium firms. Task-switching was very common for the big companies because the salesmen were not enough and when a potential buyer came, the direct manager tried to take over the negotiation and sent the salesmen to the new comer. Another common mentioned problem, was the delay generated by the customers due to the delays occurred in their workshops. Partially done work was also found in all companies. The defects are rare, majority of them are related with broken delivered products.

The analysis of 5S means sorting, setting in order, shining, standardization and sustainability. Sorting was not enough done. Many necessary things were out of the workspace, while unnecessary ones remained, especially in the small company. Setting in order was better for physical objects but not enough done for electronic devices. The salesmen from big companies could provide only standard products and the website of their supplier, without be able to present online catalogs or their own portfolio. Shining was satisfactory in all companies, the process of cleaning and organizing the workspace was quite well done. The weak point was the level of charging the electronic devices in order to show files to the potential buyer or to check previous orders. The standardization was done in theory because all salesmen from the same company had the same training, but in practice the situation was unsatisfactory. The employees from the company F provided different and wrong information. The younger person gave the worst information and when the potential buyer wanted to leave, the older salesman interferes. Instead of recognizing the bad quality of information, the first guy became very impolitely. Unfortunately was not possible a conversation with his manager to see if it is a minus in organization or a wrong person in a wrong job. Sustainability means to create a smooth workflow.

From the point of view of sales cycle, the weak aspect was at pre-sale activity. Majority of interviewed salesmen recognized that they do not put much effort in searching potential customers. They are more involved in passive sales, just waiting for the clients. There are no financial incentives in the big companies. There are some additional money in the medium company, but the salesman declared that are not enough in order to try more.

All the studied companies reach the sales goals and maybe for this reason they do not make more. All companies provided sales training modules but none of them in the lean manufacturing. None of the employees knew about what means lean or lean methodology, in spite of the fact that all the workers

from small and medium firms have university degree. This confirm the hypothesis that the concept is unknown at sales team level. None of the firms calculate the conversion rate.

The main recommendation is to include lean manufacturing trainings for the sales team. The lean methodology can be implemented in all size companies from various types of industries. Eliminating the waste in all stages of sales cycle will help organizations to become more competitive. The continuous improvement at sales process is a must. It is required to define performance indices and correlate them with lean methodology. A starting point can be the calculation of conversion rate for sales stages and the increase of it. Another recommendation is to have regular audit activity performed by supervisors in order to do things according with the standards. To create added value for the customers must remain a central aspect in the sales process. It is required to identify as much as possible the types of waste and implement plans for it in terms of quality, time and costs. The company has to learn which are the gaps between where they are and where they want to be.

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